
THE USE OF PALM KERNEL SHELL BLOCKS IN BUILDING CONSTRUCTION

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ABSTRACT

The increasing incidences of structural failures especially building collapse in recent times in Southwestern Nigeria has become worrisome in view of the damage done to adjacent structures and danger posed to building occupants and owners. There is the urgent need to devise methods to curtail failures and minimise the incidences of building collapse. This study was designed to investigate the mechanical properties of palm kernel shell (PKS) blocks in order to recommend their use in building industry. Using purposive sampling technique, a survey of 272 block industries spread across the study area was undertaken to establish the quality of sandcrete block in the circulation and their methods of production. The properties of palm kernel that are considered of importance in this study are shape, size, the void ratio, crushing strength, durability, water absorption rate, and moisture content. These were experimentally determined. After the experiments, design mix proportion was the first stage of the project followed by materials procurement as the second stage of the work. The third stage is the production of sandcrete palm kernel shell while the last stage was the determination of the mechanical properties of the block specimens. Statistical techniques of chi-square and Pearson correlations T-test were used for analysis. PKS block has lesser weight and greater crushing strength than normal sandcrete block. PKS block is a ductile material that could not suddenly break under load, without warning unlike normal sandcrete block that can suddenly collapse without warning. It is recommended that between 50 % and 60 % PKS block is adequate for walling with external plastering.

KEYWORDS: PKS Block, Sancrete Block, Ductile, Bristle, Southwestern Nigeria

Received for Publication: 16/06/13

Accepted for Publication: 22/09/13

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INTRODUCTION

In the past few decades, building collapse have been recorded across the country, the world of buildings appear to be in a precarious state; with many buildings over stressed, while some are failing at alarming rates. Housing sustainability would therefore be the obvious choice and good building materials provide an effective means of rational housing production. Sandcrete industry offers great potentials in boosting housing supply with minimal damage to the natural resources. Sandcrete is not relatively new in Nigeria. It is as old as building in Nigeria. With increasing demand for housing and inadequate supply which has led to heavy construction to the tune of billions of Naira every year. It is an indicator to the fact that something, has to be done about materials of construction. This is what has necessitated the need to look into the ways of improving on the quality of the building materials. Sandcrete being one of the major building materials is very important for the stability and durability requirement of housing and the more readily available, strong and affordable; they are the better, for the society.

However, with increase in the size of the construction industry, it has become grossly inadequate supplying good quality sandcrete needed for housing stability and there has been an increased dependence on the poor

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sandcrete for building construction in the country. Instead of leaving this industry to run down completely, the industry could be changed into a reliable and safe industry.

The provision of structures and shelters had put a lot of pressures on materials for construction in building industry in the developing part of the world. Some materials use in construction include timber, clay, bamboo, asbestos, cement, steel, raffia products, Palm Kernel Shell (PKS), wire mesh and so on. Most of these materials are now very expensive and the demand for them is far more than what can be supplied. Some of these materials, were being imported from developed countries, are classified under conventional building materials. The high demands for these conventional materials have made them to be more expensive beyond the reach of an average man. In Nigeria, various problems have been facing housing construction materials such as abuse of use of material and under utilizing to its maximum capacity, and the daily increase in prices of these materials are major causes of housing collapse in Nigeria. It is therefore very important that the cost of basic housing projects should be kept within the financial means of people by finding out suitable housing materials.

According to Dahunsi (1992), the cost of building material has increased tremendously by over one thousand percent within the past ten years or more. It is upon these problems of high cost, non availability and not measuring to man's need that has necessitated this research.

Adequate Availability of Palm Kernel Shell (PKS)

PKS is a by product in the production of palm kernel oil. It is readily available in abundance in the south and middle belt part of Nigeria. Oil palm trees grow naturally through the transpersal of seed, by animal, wind and man. Palm trees sometimes constitute nuisance to farmers where the soil is conducive with naturally fertile soil. According to Hartey (1977), over 2.46 million tonnes of palm kernel fruits bunch by weight were produced in Nigeria in 1995 out of which 1.89 million representing 76.8% of PKS were produced. In addition, Aruna (2005) found out that 1.6 million tonnes of palm kernel shells were produced from 2.06 million tonnes o palm fruits representing 77.2% by weight o total produce. The effective use of this material in housing will encourage their production, surplus manpower and boost our natural economy and serve as means of alleviating the nation from over dependent on oil boom. PKS is readily available in abundance in the rural setting to the extent that other products of oil palm and PKS are given away at relatively cheap prices and sometimes heap up at dumping sites.

ORIGIN OF PALM KERNEL TREE

According to Hartley (19977), there were diverse opinions as to the origin of palm tree. The original name of palm tree was *Elaeis guineensis*. While some opinions locates it to coastal region of the world, the works of Zeven and Rees, in 1965 that concluded with the opinion of fossil that by history and languages evidence, palm tree must have originated from African continent. Their opinion was embraced by a Portuguese's explorers of West coast of Africa at the period of slave trade. This confirms the availability of palm tree and invariably oil palm and PKS in the area.

TABLE 1: MAJOR COUNTRIES PRODUCING OIL PALM

COUNTRY	OIL PALM IN MILLION TONNES PER YEAR
Indonesia	20.9
Malaysia	17.7
Nigeria	1.5
China	1.0
Zaire (R.O.C)	0.8
Ivory Coast	0.5
Others	1.5

Source: Akomolafe (2009)

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PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF PALM KERNEL SHELL

The physical properties of palm kernel shell (PKS) that affect its quality include size, shape, density, specific gravity and porosity. The variation of these properties determines to what extent it shall be used as construction material. Palm kernel shell is light in weight as compared with other aggregates such as gravel, granite and this characteristic classified it into the classes of insulation materials. PKS possesses hard characteristics as coarse aggregate, it consists of 60-90% particles in the range of 5- 12.7 mm. the specific gravity of PKS varies between 1.17 and 1.37. The maximum thickness of palm kernel shell is about 4 mm. When mixed with concrete, the density of PKS ranges between 1700 and 2050 Kg^m-³. The water absorption varies within 23.3% in 24 hrs.

TABLE 2: PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF OIL PALM SHELL

PHYSICAL PROPERTIES	OIL PALM SHELL	INTERNET
Specific gravity (Saturated Surface Dry)	1.17	2.61
Water absorption (24 hrs)	23.32%	
Aggregate abrasion value (Los Angeles)	4.8%	
Bulk density (Compacted)	1700 Kg/ m ³	620
Fineness Modulus	6.24	

Source: <http://www.eurojournal.com/ejsr.htm>

The properties of palm kernel that are considered of importance in this study are shape, size, the void ratio, crushing strength, durability, water absorption rate, and moisture content. These were experimentally determined.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials used in this study were PKS, cement, sand, water and fabricated hand steel mould.

I. Design mix proportion

The design was based on maximum strength required for light weight block as specified in ratio 1:6. The introduction of palm kernel shell was in the proportion of 0 % PKS which means the normal sample sandcrete block. The other proportions are: 10 %; 20 %; 40 %; 50 %; 60 %; 80 %; and 100 %. These design variations are aimed at determining which ratio would be found most suitable PKS for improving the building quality in Nigeria.

II. Materials procurement

The palm kernel Shell main endocarps were obtained right away from the villagers. They normally transport PKS for sale on market days. There are two main types of PKS, the first one being “Afo” meaning washed one. It signifies that the exocarp and the mesocarp than harbour oil have been fragmented through during oil processing after the fruits enclosed by the PKS had been dried for easy removal of kernel seed. This type of PKS does not contain oil and outer skin. The stony like shell harbours the palm seed which is broken in pieces by using hand stone on a prepared small rock, or by mechanical means. They were often collected for sun drying, to remove the moisture content. This preparation was carried out by the villagers with aim of selling to interested buyers. This was sieved, sun dried before use in the most suitable state for this research. The second type of PKS does not pass through the above processes. They were bunches of rotten palm kernel fruits. That fell naturally by gravitation from the oil palm tree. The oily content does not fit for consumption, having being eaten up by animals and insects. The remnant palm fruits from the bunches fell in the forest were later handpicked by the villagers, collected, sun dried and cracked out the seeds to separate the shell from the seeds. This type of shells are called “Ira” though have biogas potentials were not considered for this research.

The cement that were used for the experiment were tested using BS 12 (1996), while water conformed to BS 3148 (1980) and the sand were tested using BS 882 (1982) standard.

- III) **BATCHING**
Batching was done by weight in ratio of 1:6 for the control sample while the ratio for the PKS block samples were varied in percentages of 10 %; 20 %; 30 %; 60 %; 80 %; and 100 % PKS respectively.
- IV) **Mixing**
The mixing was done by hand method using shovel to mix properly. Water was added just to make it moist in hand.
- V) **Moulding**
Steel hand mould was cleaned, filled with the mixed cement, sand and PKS. The mould was overturned down on a concrete floor under a shed; the mould was removed leaving the block. The process was replicated for other mixes with the exception of 80 % and 100 % mix that could not hold together. These two mixes resulted to collapse shear slump.
- VI) **Curing**
The blocks were wet cured daily starting from the second day till twenty –eight day before testing.
- VII) **Testing**
Each design mix gave out five blocks for the testing according to Nigerian Industries Standard (NIS 87: 2000). To make for comparative study, some sandcrete blocks were purchased from commercial block vendors to check for their mechanical properties. Crushing test was performed on all the prepared blocks and those purchased as required by BS 2028. The result is tabulated in Table 3. Statistical techniques of chi-square and Pearson correlations T-test were used for analysis

TABLE 3: COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH TEST RESULTS FOR PKS BLOCKS AND NORMAL SANDCRETE BLOCKS

Block size (mm)	% PKS	Crushing load (KN)	Crushing Strength (N/mm ²)	Weight (Kg)	Density (Kg/m ³)	Remarks
225 X 450	60	110.00	1.35	22.00	1057.65	PKS Block
150 X 450	60	99.00	2.10	17.00	156.71	PKS Block
150 X 450	40	57.00	1.19	17.50	1615.88	PKS Block
150 X 450	50	65.00	1.35	17.20	1588.18	PKS Block
150 X 450	20	48.00	1.00	19.10	1763.62	PKS Block
150 X 450	10	31.00	0.64	18.40	1698.98	PKS Block
225 X 450	0	75.00	0.44	22.00	1200.85	Control
150 X 450	0	60.00	2.10	19.20	1772.85	Control
150 X 450	0	62.00	2.16	17.60	2725.65	Commercial A
225 X 450	0	15.00	0.30	23.70	1037.65	Commercial B
225 X 450	0	65.00	0.78	22.50	1081.69	Commercial C
225 X 450	0	70.00	0.84	23.50	1129.77	Commercial D
150 X 450	0	60.00	2.1	18.10	2802.94	Commercial E

Source: From the Study

TEST OF HYPOTHESIS USING PEARSON CORRELATION 2- TAILED SAMPLES
 COMPARING THE WEIGHT OF PKS AND NSB

It was found out that the weight of PKS gradually decreased as the percentages of PKS increased. 0 % PKSB was 23.7Kg; 40 % was 17.5 Kg and 60 % was 17.0 Kg. judging from the Pearson correlation of 2-0.890 at alpha level of 0.05 indicates that the higher the proportion of PKS the lower the weight. This finding from the research had confirmed the literature that PKS is a lightweight material (Folayan and Marona, 1988)

Table 4 WEIGHT CORRELATION PEARSON RESULT

Correlation
 (Dataset 0)

		Descriptive Statistics		
Description	Mean	Std. Deviation	N	
PKS	30.0000	23.66432	6	
Weight	18.3800	1.54143	6	
Crushing Strength	1.2518	.48405	6	

Correlations

		PKS	Weight
PKS	Pearson Correlation sig. (2 tailed)	1	-.890*
	Sum of squares and cross products	2800.000	.017
	Covariance	560.000	-162.400
	N	6	-32.48
			6
Weight	Pearson Correlation sig. (2 tailed)	-.890*	1
	Sum of squares and cross products	11.880	2,376
	Covariance	-162.400	6
	N	-32.48	6
		6	
Crushing Strength	Pearson Correlation sig. (2 tailed)	.733	-.392
	Sum of squares and cross products	.098	.442
	Covariance	41.970	-1.464
	N	8.394	-.293
		6	6

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

COMPARING THE CRUSHING STRENGTH OF PKS AND NSB

Both the crushing strength and crushing load influenced the PKS behaviour under load. The 60 % PKSB with crushing strength of 1.4 N/ mm² and crushing load of 110 KN was higher compared to the crushing strength of 0.84 N/ mm² and crushing load of 70 KN for NSB. The result of Pearson correlation of +0.733 at 0.05 alpha level signified that the higher the proportion of PKS, the higher the crushing strength and crushing load. This finding from the research had confirmed the literature that PKS is a ductile material with low weight. NSb is prone to sudden failure under load.

Performance Rating

The performance ratings was also carried out for various mix proportion of the PKSB and the result is as contained in Tables 5 to 11

Table 5: Performance Ratings of PKSB at 0 % PKS component (NSB)

Ages (days)	Ratings of Buildings	Average Rating
0 – 9	28,20,23,25,24,26,22,23	23.88
10 – 19	41,42,40,39,40,41,39,39	40.13
20 – 29	42,45,43,43,42,44,44,42	43.13
30 – 39	46,48,47,47,46,45,45,46	46.25
40 +	51,53,55,52,51,52,52,52	52.25

Table 6: Performance Ratings of PKSB at 10 % PKS component

Ages (days)	Ratings of Buildings	Average Rating
0 – 9	21,20,22,22,22,24,22,22	19.13
10 – 19	31,30,31,31,29,29,30,29	30.00
20 – 29	31,31,32,31,33,33,33,32	32.00
30 – 39	35,34,35,36,34,34,34,36	34.75
40 +	38,38,36,38,38,38,38,38	37.75

Table 7: Performance Ratings of PKSB at 20 % PKS component

Ages (days)	Ratings of Buildings	Average Rating
0 – 9	19,17,17,17,18,18,19,19	18.00
10 – 19	25,26,28,29,25,22,28,29	26.50
20 – 29	28,27,28,27,26,28,27,29	27.50
30 – 39	28,29,28,29,29,30,28,31	29.00
40 +	31,34,32,31,35,33,34,33	32.88

Table 8: Performance Ratings of PKSB at 30 % PKS component

Ages (days)	Ratings of Buildings	Average Rating
0 – 9	21,19,20,21,20,18,20,21	20.00
10 – 19	28,30,30,31,28,30,29,28	29.25
20 – 29	34,34,34,34,32,35,33,34	33.75
30 – 39	38,37,37,39,38,38,35,37	37.38
40 +	40,39,40,38,38,39,38,38	38.75

Table 9: Performance Ratings of PKSB at 40 % PKS component

Ages (days)	Ratings of Buildings	Average Rating
0 – 9	33,33,35,34,33,33,36,35	34.00
10 – 19	31,34,34,33,33,36,36,34	33.88
20 – 29	40,38,39,43,43,38,40,39	40.00
30 – 39	44,40,42,44,44,43,46,48	43.88
40 +	47,47,46,46,47,43,45,46	46.25

Table 10: Performance Ratings of PKSB at 50 % PKS component

Ages (days)	Ratings of Buildings	Average Rating
0 – 9	20,20,21,20,20,20,20,21	20.25
10 – 19	29,28,29,30,28,29,28,28	28.63
20 – 29	31,32,32,31,30,32,31,32	31.38
30 – 39	34,33,33,36,32,32,34,34	34.75
40 +	35,35,35,34,36,35,35,37	35.13

Table 11: Performance Ratings of PKSB at 60 % PKS component

Ages (days)	Ratings of Buildings	Average Rating
0 – 9	21,20,21,20,21,20,20,21	20.50
10 – 19	32,28,29,30,30,29,29,30	29.63
20 – 29	32,32,32,33,30,32,31,33	31.88
30 – 39	34,33,33,36,34,32,34,34	32.75
40 +	35,35,35,34,36,35,35,37	35.13

t values for tables 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11 are 4.75, 1.38, -0.51, 9.39, 2.51, 0.051, 3.75 respectively indicating that there are no significant difference in the use of PKSB and NSB.

DISCUSSIONS

The results in table 3 revealed that an increase in the percentage of palm kernel shell increased the crushing load and characteristics strength. 10 % of PKS gives 31 KN crushing load and 0.64 N/ mm² crushing strength while 20 % of PKS gives 48 KN crushing load and 0.997 N/ mm² crushing strength. This phenomenon increases as the percentage of PKS increased. 60 % of PKS gives 99 KN crushing load and 2.06 N/ mm² crushing strength, this percentage completed favourably with 0 % PKS commercial sandcrete block with 62 KN crushing load and 2.16 N/ mm² crushing strength. The reasons for the above included the that the adhesion behaviours of palm kernel shells is high and this is responsible for the improvement of the crushing strength; also the ductility of PKSB is higher than that of normal sandcrete block and that PKSB gave weight and density ranges compared to normal sandcrete blocks. The increase in the compression strength of PKSB over normal sandcrete block accounts for the higher ductility and strength.

The general opinion is that heavier materials would have ability to withstand more loads and have higher strength but this research had proved the converse o the case.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

It had been concluded from the research that PKSB is a ductile material which could not easily break under load without warning unlike the NSB that would suddenly collapse without warning. It had also been confirmed that 50 % or 60 % PKS block is adequate for walling

From the above findings, it is thus recommended as follows that:

- (a) The use of PKSB should be encouraged
- (b) The Nigeria Standard organisation should formulate a standard for the use of indigenous materials
- © There should be more researches on the durability of PKSB

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